

Working Paper

Deciphering the Indus Valley Buffalo Sacrifice tablet

Vinod Aravindakshan

Adjunct Professor,

Indian Institute of Technology – Palakkad, Palakkad, Kerala, India

vinodaravindakshan@iitpkd.ac.in

Abstract

There is an absolutely new way to interpret the seals and tablets from the Indus Valley Civilization. After the absolute failure of so called “indologists” over the past hundreds of years to derive any meaning from the Indus Valley tablets, a new model is proposed. This model which is a story-based interpretation of the motifs which has never been attempted so far. I argue that the Buffalo Sacrifice tablet and other tablets acquire a totally new Dharmic meaning when interpreted as a recounting of famous Puranic stories. I have used the Puranic interpretation of Durga as a way to interpret the Buffalo Sacrifice tablet. Every figure on the tablet now acquires a new meaning. Shiva the Adi-Yogi, Durga, Mahishasura and Indra are revealed as the three mysterious figures in the tablet. This interpretation raises a question that challenges long held colonial biases of Indologists. Firstly, Puranic stories and Rig Vedic stories predate the Indus Valley Civilization. They may have emerged together and co-existed in an oral form before being written down in the Vedas and Puranas. Secondly, Shiva and Shakti were prominent deities worshipped in the Indus Valley. Thirdly, the Indus Valley Civilization was completely Hindu in character and essence.

Keywords: Buffalo Sacrifice tablet, Indus Valley, Shiva, Shakti, Indra, Mohenjo-daro, Harappa

Working Paper

1. Introduction

The Buffalo Sacrifice tablet is one of the mysterious tablets from Harappa, Indus Valley Civilization, from possibly around 3000 BCE. It is one of the most puzzling figures of the Indus Valley. Some think it is a buffalo sacrifice, based on similar rituals in other civilizations. However, a male sitting non-chalantly while a women does the difficult work of killing raises a lot of questions which have no answers.

Figure 1: The Buffalo Sacrifice Tablet

Source: <https://www.harappa.com/blog/buffalo-sacrifice>

The Indus Valley seals and tablets are one of the most unencrypted codes of all time. Everyone has tried all sorts of decryption techniques, but none has worked. How is it possible that people around 5000 years ago could come up with something that the most brilliant minds today cannot crack?

I would argue that maybe everyone is searching in the wrong place for answers. Maybe there is something which everyone is missing.

2. Methods

Let us look at this 1800 CE image below. A child in India can tell you what this image is. It represents the story of Ma Durga killing Mahishasura. We will then compare this image to the Indus Valley tablet.

Working Paper

Figure 2: The killing of Mahishasura

Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mahishasura>

This is but a very common image found in almost every temple to Shakti. Such iconography and images are found everywhere in temples and in households in India. When one compares this popular image with the Indus Valley tablet, the following facts emerge.

- The first similarity is that of a woman attacking the bovine. At first glance, it is not clear whether the bovine is a cow or buffalo. A woman attacking a bovine alone is certainly unique. If stone age women were demure and a prisoner of the stone age men, that western account definitely does not apply to the Indus Valley. Either people in India were sending women to battle alone or this seal represents religious iconography.
- There is a three-pronged instrument in the hands of the woman. She is literally immersed in "taking the bull by the horns." Three pronged instruments are rare anywhere in the world. For an Indian accustomed to Indian culture, the three-pronged instrument looks exactly like a trishul, the trident of Lord Shiva. The picture of a trident is enclosed below. Is it similar? The central point extends beyond the right and left points and that is confirmed in the seal.

Figure 3: The Trishul

Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trishula>

Working Paper

Now we have to answer other questions:

- Is this bovine a cow or buffalo?
- How is the person behind the woman seemingly floating on air?
- What is the crocodile doing above the bovine?

Regarding question 1), the answer is easy. Cows in the Indus Valley looked like the image below.

Figure 4: Seal with Two-Horned Bull

Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Clevelandart_1973.160.jpg

Hence, it is definitely not a cow. The only option left for the bovine is that of a buffalo.

Regarding question 2, the person behind has been identified as a yogi in a yogic pose. This icon also appears in the Pashupati seal shown below.

Figure 5: The Pashupati Seal

Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pashupati_seal

Working Paper

It is a non-brainer to any Indian that the icon is Shiva. There are other seals of the same yogi, which makes it even more clear. The yogi is surrounded by animals. Is that a reference to Pasupati? The meditation pose cannot be ignored. This is probably the oldest symbol of classical meditation in the world.

Who is the first yogi - the Adi Yogi? It is again Shiva. He is always seen in eternal Dhyana or meditation. That also explains why he is floating on air in the battle. He is the consciousness Atman pushing the woman to the fight. That woman is none other than Shakti. Even today, Indians say that wherever there is Shiva, there is Shakti. Both are equals and represent the Brahman as Shiva-Shakti.

Now is the tricky third question. What is the crocodile doing above the buffalo? Crocodiles are a very rare occurrence in Hindu theology or stories. However, there is an interesting story of a crocodile in the story of Mahishasura. The crocodile represents Indra and Indra actually tries to kill Mahishasura father, Rambha and ends up killing Rambha's brother, Karamba, when both indulged in intense penance to further evil in the world. The crocodile represents the force of goodness that brought an end to the evil of Mahishasura's forefathers. What Indra could not accomplish fully, Durga was able to accomplish. The seal suggests that while Indra and Durga were fighting, the consciousness that animated both of them belonged to the Adi Yogi, Shiva. Unknown to all, it was Shiva, the Brahman, himself who was fighting the forces of evil in his two forms as Indra and Durga.

3. Results

Four myths are challenged by this interpretation. The revised interpretations are:

1) Shiva is a Vedic-Puranic construct: My interpretation questions a lot of holy grail assumptions made by the "famous" indologists. The first assumption is Shiva was absent in the Vedas and Indus Valley culture. When I checked, Shiva's name appears 65 times in the Rig Veda and the yogi in the tablet is clearly Shiva. The second assumption is that women were subservient and were enslaved in ancient India. This seal clearly proves that wrong. The third assumption is that Durga is a recent invention of the Hindus, in the last 1000 years and that too only in the Puranas. Durga's name appears in the Rig Veda multiple times including verses 4.28, 5.34, 8.27, 8.47, 8.93 and 10.127.

2) Shiva-Shakti existed prior to the Vedas: The divinization of the feminine as equal to the masculine divinity in the form of Shiva Shakti, is a direct challenge to a western conception that the highest divinity is purely masculine. The emancipation of women in the west still suffers a huge problem - the western model still refuses to accept that man and woman can be equal at the highest level. No such problem exists in India and that also is a problem for the west. If Durga is found to be older than a thousand years, this upsets all the fanciful western misconceptions about India.

3) The Indus Valley was completely Hindu: The Rig Veda is much older than the Indus Valley. It was an oral tradition for thousands of years, before it was written down on paper. If it is found that Indus Valley folks knew about the stories from the Vedas and Puranas, that means that these stories were circulated orally for many thousands of years before it was written down on paper. To connect the Indus Valley to the Vedas would challenge how Indian

Working Paper

history was interpreted by the west. Nobody likes a challenge or to be told that their civilization is five to seven thousand years younger than India. The colonial powers do not like to be reminded that they are a pup on the block. If IVC was Hindu, killing cows would have been taboo. Hence, the indologist interpretation of buffalo-sacrifice would have been the explanation furthest away from the truth.

4) Folklore is the key: Nobody has ever tried to apply a Hindu Puranic framework to interpret the seals. Most of the self-proclaimed "indologists" know next to nothing about the deeper meaning of Indian rituals and stories. They will be quick to slam any attempt to re-interpret the Indus Valley seals, though they are themselves intellectually bankrupt about how to interpret them.

4. Discussion

We ask two questions as part of the discussion:

1) Is this a fanciful interpretation?

Let us look at the words describing the death of Mahishasura from the Markandeya Purana - "She then pounced on Mahishasura, pushing him to the ground with her left leg. She grasped his head in one hand, pierced him with her sharp trident held in another, and with yet another of her ten hands she wielded her bright sword, beheading him."

Compare that with the seal. The buffalo is clearly on the ground under the leg. The horn is grasped with one and the trident on the other hand does pierce the body. The only thing missing in the seal are the other manifold hands of Durga. That difference can be attributed to differences in iconography and its evolution over many thousands of years.

2) Why haven't others thought of such an explanation?

Historians are not very intelligent people. The smartest people get into engineering or medicine or business. Even among Historians, the dumbest of the dumb ones turn historians. So "reputed" Indologists like Asko Parpallo have no idea what this seal stands for. They cannot make meaning out of even one symbol. He terms this seal that of a "water-buffalo sacrifice." He and his colleagues then connect this seal to some random ritual from Tamil Nadu (from where I hail from) and then try to denigrate the both the seal and the ritual in the most demeaning and caustic way possible. Ask also manages to bring some tripe about Brahminical oppression into this Indus Valley conversation. This is a reminder to Indians that if they do not try to interpret their own icons and history, others will do it for them in a way that advances their own agenda. Colonial agendas still run riot when it comes to the Indus Valley interpretations.

5. Conclusion

Indus Valley tablets and seals have a lot of religious, story based and Puranic meaning embedded in them. Just as I have done here with the Buffalo Sacrifice Seal, similar efforts should be made with other seals and tablets. A devotional attitude of Bhakti and a cultural understanding of Indian stories is grossly missing in Indologists today. Without the right attitude, The Indus Valley code can never be cracked.

Working Paper

References

- Meadow R. (n.d.). How common is the yogi figure, possibly proto-Shiva figure, across various Indus sites? Retrieved September 7, 2024, available at <https://www.harappa.com/answers/how-common-yogi-figure-possibly-proto-shiva-figure-across-various-indus-sites>
- Parpola A. (2015), *The Roots of Hinduism*, Oxford University Press, pp. 175-176, p. 178
- Ratnagar S. (n.d.). How common is the yogi figure, possibly proto-Shiva figure, across various Indus sites? Retrieved September 7, 2024, available at <https://www.harappa.com/answers/how-common-yogi-figure-possibly-proto-shiva-figure-across-various-indus-sites>
- Aravindakshan, V. (2025). The Vaishnavite interpretation of the Indus Valley Pashupati Seal. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15830143>